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Remarking An Analisation

The Idea of Simplification of Problem Using Modified Basis

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Abstract

Diagonalised matrix acts as an operator and here our work is to implement diagonal matrix as a basis of structures and simplifies the function of an operators . This new form of basis helps to understand the functional structure . Finally we have developed the relationship between diagonalisation and Gram-Schmidt condition of ortho-normalisation.

Keywords Basis, Orthogonalisation, Eigen Value and Eigen Vectors, Linear Dependence.

Introduction

For describing any physical picture simple or complex we need proper axis. These axis is basis. Here we actually show by proper choice of basis the complicated geometrical and physical picture becomes simple. Then we will show the new concept that diagonalisation is nothing but the Gram-Schmidt orthogonal process. That is a serious statement. No one dares to say this till now. In different steps of linear algebra we do these two things separately and they have different applications in various field. But this paper enable us to show that these two things are not separate and basically giving the identical direction for solving the problem.

Objective of study

Here main objective is to find the different suitable basis for solving different mathematical representation of physical problem. This aim forces us to find orthogonal frame of reference which is basically orthonormal basis. By setting orthonormal basis we can simply visualize the behaviour of a function in physical picture. That means the angle between each coordinates and the angle produced by a definite vector with certain coordinate and their change can be observed. This realisation helps to find the internal structure of functions and operators and picture of simultaneous operators.

Review of Literature

Diagonalisation is a very important mathematical tool used in linear algebra , and it has many advantages and can be applied in various field of applications .It presents the problem in more simple way. Matrices are randomized by joint diagonalisation method for finding optimization problem[1]. Asymptotical diagonalisation algorithm are used for a class of sparse hermitian matrices for perturbation of particular row or column [2]. Eigen value and eigen vectors are used in diagonalisation of a square matrix using Caley – Hamilton theorem and it gives a new way to find inverse of a matrix [3]. Simultaneous diagonalisation is used as a subroutine in many machine learning problem including blind source separation and parameter estimation[4]. There are so many uses of matrices in real life problem [5]. There are so many work in this new field of work and it is a good topic in linear algebra to find new field of applications

Main Text

A basis is something like the reference axis. In context of vector algebra any vector space is a sequence of vectors with two properties.

1. The vectors are independent.
2. They span the space completely .
3. The operation between vectors are such that they can be added or can be multiplied by scalars .

Let $V = a_1v_1 + a_2v_2 + a_3v_3 + \dots$ where v_1, v_2, v_3 are independent vectors and a_1, a_2 and a_3 are only some numerical multipliers .There is only one way to write any vectors as a linear combination. A vector space has an infinitely many different basis. The number of basis vectors are representing the dimensionality of the vector space . So basis mainly dimensionality indicator. The basis is the maximum number of independent set of vectors. It can not be made larger in number without losing its independence. We generally choose the perpendicular basis. It helps to construct the easier geometric thinking with the concept of algebraic idea. The compulsion is not that of orthogonality. The idea of orthogonal vectors helps to control the basis from the problem of underflow or overflow. The length of basis vectors should be unity to introduce the idea of normalisation .

For orthogonal vectors $X^T Y = x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + x_3y_3 + x_4y_4 + \dots = 0$

Where X and Y are two independent vectors having a same number of components , that means they are of same dimensions. $X^T Y$ indicates the inner products which can be expressed as matrix form. It is sometimes called scalar product and can be expressed as $X \cdot Y$, which basically indicates the measurement of length and is a dimensionless quantity .

$$X^T Y = [x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, \dots] \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \\ \dots \end{bmatrix}$$

Most important fact is that ,if non zero vectors V_1, V_2 and V_3 are mutually orthogonal then those vectors will be linearly independent automatically. This is one of the most advantageous properties of orthogonality .

Our discussion is mainly about the functional basis which are called operators. To understand proper functioning of the operators we need the suitable basis that simplifies the structure of operator . If we can find the basis that diagonalise the operator then it is helpful to understand the functioning of operator and their structure becomes simple.

Let we have operator T and this operator is diagonal in u basis. That means

$$T U_i = \sum T_{ki} U_k .$$

For being diagonal the sum will work only when $k=i$ that means

$$T U_i = \sum T_{ii} U_i$$

$$\text{Or } T U_i = \lambda_i U_i$$

Next we have vector space $V (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots)$ and in this basis the operator is not diagonal . Here we will try to change the basis where system in new frame looks to be diagonal.

Let A is the linear operator which changes the basis.

$$\text{Then } U_k = A V_k$$

And

$$T\{U\} = A^{-1} T(\{V\}) A$$

$$T_{ij}\{U\} = (A^{-1})_{ik} T_{kp}\{v\} A_{pj}$$

Here $A^{-1}TA$ acts as an operator which is diagonal in U basis. There is a definite proof of it.

$$T U_i = \lambda_i U_i$$

$$\text{Here } U_i = AV_i$$

$$T A V_i = \lambda_i A V_i$$

$$A^{-1} T A V_i = A^{-1} A \lambda_i V_i$$

$$(A^{-1}TA) V_i = A^{-1} A \lambda_i V_i$$

$$= \lambda_i V_i$$

It shows new form $A^{-1}TA$ is actually an operator which is diagonal in V basis. The above mathematical procedure helps us to find the suitable basis that makes the operator diagonal. Here this procedure is known as similarity procedure.

Unitarily Diagonalizable operator

The unitary diagonalisation is possible only when our basis vectors are obtained from eigen values. Hermitian, antihermitian and unitary operators have some special properties by which they can be diagonalised unitarily. These are commonly called normal operators. These three operators follow the relations $[N^+, N] = 0$, where these operators have a special name called the normal operator.

Let D_M is a diagonal matrix. This is another normal matrix N. Now we can write

$$U^+ N U = D_N$$

$$N = U D_N U^+$$

$$N^+ = U D_N^+ U^+$$

$$\text{Accordingly } N N^+ = U D_N U^{-1} U D_N^+ U^+$$

$$= U D_N D_N^+ U^+$$

$$N^+ N = U D_N^+ U^+ U D_N U^+$$

$$= U D_N^+ D_N U^+$$

$$\text{Thus } [N, N^+] = U \{D_N^+ D_N - D_N D_N^+\}$$

$$= U \{0\} U^+$$

=0 So our statement is true and applicable in all the cases .

In complex vector space the matrix must have one real eigen value . Then pick up the eigen value and eigen vector and new form of matrix that will contain a lot of zeros . This idea will help us to determine the simultaneous diagonalisation .

$$\begin{pmatrix} \lambda & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Simultaneous Diagonalisation

Sometimes we need to diagonalize more than one operators. Here exists some basis which is effective for both the operators . Let S and T are two operators belonging to vector space V and can be simultaneously diagonalizable . It is possible if there exists a set of basis vector for which every basis vector is the eigen state of both the operators S and T equally . So S and T operators have a common eigenstate and this clearly says that the condition of simultaneous diagonalisation is commutative form .

The condition for commutation and non commutation depends on the availability of suitable dependency of the basis . If two operators do not commute then their operation gives some particular result that can be observed in any basis . The advantage of diagonal matrix or diagonal operators are that is they must commute according to their physical structure . The situation changes when operator changes its nature . Such operators may be degenerate or non degenerate . In this two different situation we have to use different mathematical concept according to the type and availability of the basis .

Case I

When one operator is non degenerate (T) and other becomes degenerate or non-degenerate (S) .

Let $TU_i = \lambda_i U_i$ where $\lambda_i = \lambda_j$ when $i=j$.

In this situation the eigen values are different and eigen vectors form the invariant subspace .

Here $S(TU_i) = S(\lambda_i U_i)$

$STU_i = \lambda_i SU_i$

$TSU_i = \lambda_i SU_i$

$T(Su_i) = \lambda_i(Su_i)$

This is possible since S and T commute .

It shows Vector Su_i can be expressed in the invariant subspace U_i . SU_i can not belong to any subspace because all eigen values are different . Thus all the eigen states U_i are simultaneously eigen states of T and S .

Case II

Both S and T are degenerate .

In degenerate state, most of the states are of more than 1 dimensions . Here representation of state $U_k = \{ U | SU = Au \}$ and dimension $U_k = d_k$. It indicates for a particular eigen value there are a number of eigen vectors . The different eigen vectors

form a space called degenerate sub space . So the subspace $U_k = \{ U \mid SU = \lambda U \}$ by the basis vectors have same dimensionality .

Let we have a subspace like a cone . Here every vectors are eigen vectors . If we scale by a multiplier then all vectors will get same effect. This can be expressed by

$$U_k = (U_1^{(1)}, U_2^{(1)}, U_3^{(1)} \dots U_d^{(1)})$$

$$(U_1^{(2)}, U_2^{(2)}, U_3^{(2)} \dots U_d^{(2)})$$

.....

$$(U_1^{(m)}, U_2^{(m)}, U_3^{(m)} \dots U_d^{(m)})$$

Operators S is diagonal on this basis. Since every vector in the { V } space are vectors of S ,so operator S looks like a diagonal matrix . This simply indicates U_k is an invariant subspace of the operator S and T . Finally they are in a position of commutation .

$$S(TU) = T(SU)$$

$$= \lambda_k(TU).$$

Here TU is the invariant subspace . This physical concept can be made by block diagonal technique

So in both the cases the diagonalisation is possible. According to the problem we have to change the nature of basis and it makes the solution .

Gram Schmidt condition of orthonormalisation and its comparison with diagonalisation

Next our approach is to understand the orthogonalization by Gram Schmidt methods and to compare with diagonalisation technique .

Let we have a set of common basis vectors a_1 and a_2 and we want to change in the form of orthogonal basis in terms of b_1 and b_2 . Our natural choice is $a_1 = b_1$ by making unity in magnitude . Now to get orthogonal form of b_2 , we draw a perpendicular at the tip of vector a_1 . So we are taking as a orthogonal component of a_1 . This is shown in picture. This is basically the orthogonalisation procedure. The process becomes easy if we made each vector by unity length. This unity formation is called normalisation.

Finally we have made an orthonormal basis in spitted form. If these vectors can be expressed as a matrix then they will form a orthonormal matrix. So we found the same results are obtained in two procedure. One in algebraic process which is diagonalisation and other is geometric process known as Gram- Schmidt orthogonalisation process.

Conclusion

It is found that any operator or transformation can be expressed by a number of ways. This helps to describe the problem in a simple manner. That requires a proper reference frame and the diagonal basis is one such choice. It makes the problem more simple to understand and for further development. Here two methods diagonalisation and as Gram-Schmidt orthogonalisation are exactly the same thing.

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